

IGTFInfo Trust Anchor and Policy meta-data specification

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The IGTF Distribution, as well as similar distributions built by relying parties and including EGI and wLCG, provide additional meta-data alongside the trust anchors. These IGTFInfo ('.info') files contain information about the trust anchor and may be used by supporting tools like [fetch-crl\(8\)](#), monitoring tools, and in security incident response. This document described the syntax and semantics of the IGTF info files for trust anchors and the policy information contained therein, as well as the naming of these files used to associate them to the corresponding trust anchor.

Naming of the IGTFInfo files

For meta-data corresponding to a *trust anchor*, the name of the file shall be based on the IGTF designated short-name ("alias") of the trust anchor. Each trust anchor package contains a single PKI CA certificate, and each meta-data file shall correspond to a single trust anchor. Trust anchor alias names shall not start with with the string literal 'policy-'.

For meta-data corresponding to a *policy* (trust anchor grouping), the name of the file shall start with the character sequence "policy-". For example, the information about the list of IGTF Classic CAs shall be named "policy-igtf-classic.info".

For example, for the CA with the alias "NIKHEF" (which happens to have the subject-DN "/C=NL/O=NIKHEF/CN=NIKHEF medium-security certification auth") and a trust anchor file name "NIKHEF.pem", the meta-data file is named "NIKHEF.info".

Meta-data file syntax

The IGTFInfo file is a plain-text 7-bit ASCII file containing name-value pairs.

- The name and value are separated by an EQUAL ("=", 0x3d) character. White space immediately preceding or following the first equal sign of a line shall be ignored, and is neither part of the name nor of the value of the name-value pair.
- Each line shall be terminated with a LF ("\n", 0x0a) character.
- A line continuation shall consist of a BACKSLASH ("\", 0x5c) character followed by a LF ("\n") character. Both characters shall be discarded on read.
- Initial white space on a line, name, or value shall be ignored.

- Trailing whitespace on a line, name, or value shall be ignored.
- Any characters on a logical line including and following a HASH ("#", 0x23) character up to and including the LF ("\n") character shall be ignored (these are to be treated as comments). Line continuation shall be applied before comment identification.
- Some values, if so indicated below, either MAY or SHALL (when so indicated in the attribute specification) be quoted using DOUBLE QUOTES ("", 0x22) to prevent ambiguity. If and only if quoted, the content of the so-quoted string shall be minimally URL-encoded to prevent the occurrence of: double quotes ("", 0x22), PERCENT ("%", 0x25), NEWLINE (0x0a), and backslash ("", 0x5c) within the string. For example, the string '/CN=David "0% op 100% Bob" Groep' shall be quoted as '/CN=David %220%25 op 100%25Bob%22 Groep'.

Attributes

name	description
alias	Shortname of the trust anchor or policy. REQUIRED for trust anchors, OPTIONAL for policies
version	Version of the trust anchor package. Usually assigned externally based on the over-all distribution version. REQUIRED for both trust anchors and policies
crl_url	Semi-colon separated list of HTTP URLs. This information is also used by the IGTF distribution build process to generate the legacy crl_url files. Required for trust anchors, not used for policies.
email	An RFC2882 internet email address for the emergency or concerns contact for this trust anchor. REQUIRED for trust anchors, not used for policies.
status	The IGTF (or RP) accreditation status of the trust anchor. For IGTF accredited trust anchors, the key word "accredited" must be followed by a COLON and the name of the authentication profile. For example: "status=experimental", or "status=accredited:mics". When the status is set to "discontinued", the IGTF distribution will not include this trust anchor. Permitted values for trust anchors: discontinued, experimental, unaccredited, accredited:classic, accredited:mics, accredited:slcs, accredited:iota. REQUIRED for trust anchors, not used for policies.
sha1fp.0	The SHA-1 fingerprint of the public key data in the trust anchor certificate. The ".0" is the sequence number of the certificate in the package, and is always zero. RECOMMENDED for trust anchors, not used for policies.

name	description
url	URL to a general public information page for the CA, accrediting body, or RP. OPTIONAL
ca_url	URL to a PEM or DER formatted certificate, i.e. the trust anchor to which it corresponds. OPTIONAL
policy_url	URL to a document (or page containing links to documents) for the Certificate Policy and Practice Statements for this trust anchor. OPTIONAL
subjectdn	The "quoted" subjectDN of the trust anchor (i.e. the subject DN of the cert) for trust anchors. For policies, it is the comma-separated list of quoted subjectDNs of all trust anchors that comply with this policy, and it must correspond to the list of trust anchors named in the "requires" attribute. When present, this value MUST always be quoted, even if it does not contain whitespace. OPTIONAL

name	description
requires	The set of alias names for all other trust anchors that need to be installed for this specific trust anchor to be usable. For policies, contains the list of all acceptable trust anchors under this policy. REQUIRED for policies, REQUIRED for subordinate trust anchors where a higher-level CA is included in the same policy package and distribution.
obsoletes	The set of alias names for all trust anchors that once were accredited and to be installed, but that have been withdrawn and must no longer be used. For policies only. RECOMMENDED in policy files when trust anchors are removed in an updated release of the same policy bundle.

Examples

Example trust anchor IGTFInfo file content

```
#
# Information for /DC=com/DC=DigiCert-Grid/O=DigiCert Grid/CN=DigiCert Grid Trust
CA G2
#
alias = DigiCertGridTrustCAG2-Classic
ca_url = http://www.digicert-grid.com/DigiCertGridTrustCAG2_text.txt
crl_url =
http://crl3.digicert.com/DigiCertGridTrustCAG2.crl;http://crl4.digicert.com/Digi
CertGridTrustCAG2.crl
email = support@DigiCert.com
status = accredited:classic
url = http://www.DigiCert-Grid.com/
requires = DigiCertAssuredIDRootCA-Root
version = 1.64
sha1fp.0 = 06:01:40:42:57:78:0C:9F:E6:B3:D9:03:72:80:3F:38:EE:3A:60:6A
subjectdn = "/C=US/O=DigiCert Grid/OU=www.digicert.com/CN=DigiCert Grid Trust CA
G2"
```

Example for a policy IGTFInfo file (in this case the 'slcs' policy):

```
# @(#)policy-igtfslcs.info - IGTF slcs authorities
# Generated Tuesday, 09 Jun, 2015
version = 1.65
requires = NCSA-slcs-2013 = 1.65, \
    DFN-SLCS = 1.65, \
    PSC-Myproxy-CA = 1.65, \
    FNAL-SLCS = 1.65, \
    NCSA-tfca-2013 = 1.65, \
    NERSC-SLCS = 1.65
subjectdn = "/C=US/O=National Center for Supercomputing
Applications/OU=Certificate Authorities/CN=MyProxy CA 2013", \
    "/C=DE/O=DFN-Verein/OU=DFN-PKI/CN=DFN SLCS-CA", \
    "/C=US/O=Pittsburgh Supercomputing Center/CN=PSC MyProxy CA", \
    "/DC=gov/DC=fnal/O=Fermilab/OU=Certificate Authorities/CN=Kerberized CA HSM",
\
    "/C=US/O=National Center for Supercomputing Applications/OU=Certificate
Authorities/CN=Two Factor CA 2013", \
    "/DC=net/DC=ES/OU=Certificate Authorities/CN=NERSC Online CA"
obsoletes = SWITCHslcs, \
    ncsa-gridshib-ca, \
    SWITCHslcs2011, \
    NCSA-tfca, \
    NICS-MyProxy, \
    NCSA-slcs
```

Notes

The regular IGTF policy packages are built only for accreditation profiles (Classic, MICS, SLCS, IOTA), but there are intentionally "no" RPM meta-packages for experimental, or the discontinued CAs (why would one want to install the discontinued ones?). But the tar.gz file does contain the "policy-igtf-discontinued.info" file. This can be used by .eg. monitoring to check if discontinued CAs are still found in production (whereas they should not be there).

Version history

version	date	editor	changes
1.0 R1	2015-06-09	davidg	initial version
1.0 R2	2015-06-18	davidg	fixed typographical issues
1.0 R3	2016-10-13	davidg	fixed typographical issues
1.1	2025-06-20	davidg	retypeset in markdown and clarified normative language